

Dark pattern marketing and it's consequences: How 'Dark' pattern marketing techniques influence purchasing decisions among Indian teenagers.

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Abstract

Dark pattern marketing is an invasive marketing tactic that relies on manipulating users psychologically to increase sales. This paper evaluates the impacts of these tactics and how they influence purchasing decisions. The study makes use of primary research as a means of data analysis starting with three baseline hypotheses of expected consumer behavior. The three hypotheses predict that teens are unaware of their interaction with dark pattern marketing, their purchasing decisions are more impulsive than rational and their emotions have an effect on their final purchasing decisions. The data is gathered from a diverse participant pool of 46 observations across different genders, socio-economic backgrounds, and their cities of residence. The primary goal of the paper is to spread awareness of the impacts of dark marketing tactics as well as understand the underlying effects. The findings indicate that exposure to dark patterns does not notably influence the decision-making processes of Indian teenagers; instead, it appears to be a passive experience. One potential explanation could be rooted in cultural differences. As consumerism grows, research about the beauty industry is very less but necessary, noticing the current rising trend of problematic and unethical marketing tactics employed by brands such as targeting children by exploiting their fear of missing out. This paper helps increase awareness as well as information about the current purchasing patterns of Indian teenagers. It also provides policymakers more material and context to work with especially since the government is putting additional efforts in minimizing the use of such tactics.

Keywords: Dark pattern marketing, Online consumerism, Indian teenagers, Online marketing

1. Introduction

Living in today's fast-paced consumerist world, online shopping has reached new extents every day, as is predicted, India's current 100 million online shoppers will group up to 350

million by 2025 and daily shipments would grow from the current 8 million to about 25 million which is a 40% annual growth rate (GLG network member, 2021). There are certainly multiple benefits of to consumers like not needing to visit overcrowded markets, having a wide variety of products to choose from at fingertips, and easily comparing blockbuster deals (Maheshwari 2023). The initial increase was seen during the Covid-19 lockdown when e-commerce became help support for both consumers who could access essential commodities and hygiene products as well and producers as they had a larger business avenue (Seth et al 2021). This rise also led to growth of living styles and convenience as people adopted to better and finer technology. The rapid ascent of e-commerce also have had negative impacts like on traditional retailers who have not been able tot keep up the accessibility, ease and comfort that comes along with online shopping (Tiwari et al, 2023). It, however, has multiple hidden issues which are not well known or cared about. One of them is dark pattern marketing or invasive marketing where firms incorporate hidden marketing tactics often as an attempt of boosting sales and earning a greater profit margin in the short term.

First coined by UX specialist Harry Brignull, the term ‘dark pattern marketing’ describes the way in which software can subtly trick users into taking actions or making purchases they didn’t mean to originally (Ravencraft, 2020). This involves everything from cookie pop-ups to ads which don't close and lead to sketchy websites usually selling something which is broadly perceived negatively and ends up hurting brands more than the consumers (Correa, 2022). These tactics are not always troublesome but often also present themselves in forms of non-existent sales and never-ending countdowns. These tactics make website interface hard to use and navigate through and make it challenging and frustrating to find products that the consumer actually wants to consume (ForumIAS, 2023). The majority of consumers of these UI/UX software remain unaware of the invasive and exploitative nature of the techniques, which Brignull (2010) describes as “a user interface that has been carefully crafted to trick users into doing things that are not in their interest and usually at their expense”.

Other explicit examples of dark patterns include masked advertising, which is when an advertisement looks differently than it does, forced continuation, which is when a paid subscription is continued without notification after the trial period ends, involuntary social media friend spamming, hidden costs, which occur when expenses in online stores are not disclosed when the user expects them to be, and disorientation. There are also subtler

practices, such as pseudo-notifications (when notifications that are not important are sent to users). These patterns can manifest in different forms such as drip pricing, trick questions, nagging, disguised ads, bait and switch, roach motel confirm shaming etc.

The consequences of this often end up looking like users not wanting to shop from the firm after that purchase. While these tactics work for the short term, they hurt the firms in the long run as they are unable to form loyal customer bases. As usage of internet has increased, awareness about such tactics has definitely increased. However, they still impact the children as well as the older generation which is a huge target demographic. Dark patterns are not only unethical towards the user, are unethical even to the competition (Day & Stemler, 2019). Though considerable research has been done on the subject, additional academic research is needed to increase the public's understanding of it. The primary objective of this paper is to increase information and awareness of this phenomena in the specific niche of beauty industry.

2. Literature review

This section provides an overview of relevant literature concerning dark patterns. It highlights results, illustrates the development of previous research, and gives an insight into the background and motives of research conducted.

Pomeranz 2011 scrutinizes the FTC's role in regulating marketing directed at children highlighting the distinction between misleading and unfair rulemaking within the context of the First Amendment. The study emphasizes the necessity for regulation in light of the substantial expenditure on marketing targeted at children.

Kim et al 2013 investigate the impact of dark pattern tactics on consumers' perceptions and attitudes towards online travel agencies OT in the tourism industry. Their work reveals the moderating effects of social proof and moral identity on consumers' responses to dark patterns shedding light on the financial consequences for consumers due to OTA booking scams.

Gambio et al 2016 explore individuals' cognitive heuristics when disclosing or withholding information online. Their analysis reveals various positive and negative heuristics influencing

privacy behaviors providing insights into the psychological factors driving individuals' online decision-making.

Day 2019 highlights the deceptive nature of digital manipulation which undermines users' capacity for rational decision-making and empowers platforms to amass wealth without relying on the merit of their offerings. This research underscores the need to recognize and address the manipulative tactics employed in digital environments.

Cara 2019 investigates the impacts of dark patterns across various web products emphasizing the ethical concerns raised by their ubiquity. The study underscores the challenge of regulating deceptive techniques and advocates for user-centric design principles to mitigate the exploitation of cognitive biases.

Bosch et al 2016 examine the strategies used by online service providers to deceive users into disclosing personal information. The findings highlight the prevalence of privacy dark patterns in online platforms shedding light on the deceptive manipulation of individuals for data collection purposes.

Waldman 2020 explores how people perceive difficulty in decision-making processes, particularly in safeguarding online privacy. The study shows how users' interpretations of difficulty influence their actions with implications for online behavior and privacy management.

Luguri 2021 identifies and categorizes dark patterns in online marketing emphasizing their deceptive nature and effectiveness in persuading consumers. The study highlights the dangers posed by subtle dark patterns which can influence consumers without causing apparent annoyance raising concerns about consumer protection and ethical marketing practices

Lastly, Trzaskowski 2023 examines the relationship between behavior modification regulation and choice architecture design within European Union data protection and marketing laws. The study emphasizes the importance of ensuring informed consent and preventing manipulative commercial practices highlighting the regulatory challenges in digital environments.

The studies by Gambio et al 2016 and Waldman 2020 both delve into users' decision-making processes online focusing on cognitive heuristics like loss aversion fallacy and perceptions of difficulty respectively. These themes intersect with insights from other studies on dark pattern marketing highlighting the interdisciplinary nature of research in this field.

Runge 2022 investigates the relative difficulty of canceling website subscriptions compared to signing up for them shedding light on the use of dark patterns to discourage account deletion and promote continued engagement. Similarly, Sin et al 2022 delve into the effectiveness of dark patterns in promoting impulsive online purchases and evaluate behaviorally informed interventions to mitigate their impact emphasizing the significance of these interventions in combating deceptive design elements.

These studies collectively contribute to the literature on dark pattern marketing by exploring various facets of deceptive design practices, their effects on consumer behavior and regulatory implications. The findings underscore the importance of ethical considerations user empowerment and regulatory interventions in addressing the challenges posed by dark patterns in digital environments.

The present study aims to extend this research by investigating the effectiveness of behaviorally informed interventions in mitigating the impact of dark patterns on consumer decision-making in the context of e-commerce websites by employing experimental methods grounded in normative perspectives This research seeks to provide insights into effective strategies for combating deceptive marketing tactics online and promoting consumer welfare.

3. Methodology

This research paper aims to provide comprehensive information on the techniques used in exploring the effects of dark pattern marketing on Indian teenagers' purchasing behavior within the beauty industry, as depicted in the data section.

On the basis of the literature section, the main hypotheses guiding the design of the questionnaire were:

Alternative H1: Indian teenagers who buy cosmetics online are unaware of their exposure to dark pattern marketing.

Alternative H2: Teenagers in India who are exposed to beauty industry dark pattern

marketing are more prone to making impulsive purchases.

Alternative H3: Teenagers' emotional reactions have an effect on their final judgments while making purchases online, which helps understand the coercive nature of these marketing techniques.

Null H1: Indian teenagers were aware of their exposure to dark pattern marketing when buying cosmetics online

Null H2: Teenagers in India who are exposed to beauty industry dark pattern marketing are lesser prone to making impulsive purchases.

Null H3: Teenagers' emotional reactions do not have an effect on their final judgments while making purchases online.

Utilizing primary data obtained through online survey, the study examines dark pattern marketing's impact on consumer decision-making. This questionnaire aims to explore the intricacies of the beauty industry online space and specifically the dark pattern techniques used and their impact. It questions the manipulatory tactics and the frequency of their use, which is related to product choice. The survey also explores the aftermath of these coercive purchases, looking into the impacts on individuals in their purchases.

The data set for this study includes responses from various Indian adolescents exposed to online cosmetic products. The survey consists of general questions to help segment respondents based on demographics, online shopping habits (Figure 2) and feelings about shopping impact. This comprehensive approach will help provide a more nuanced understanding of how dark markets operate in the beauty industry and among youth groups in India.

The final data set obtained through the questionnaire consists of 46 observations. This study used primary research as the main source of data, using an extensive questionnaire to gather information. The participant pool was of 46 people varying in age, gender and place of origin. Of the 46, 63% were below the age range of 30 while the rest were above. 63% of the participants were also female while the rest being male. The places were different cities and towns of India ranging from the less developed like Nathdwara to the metropolitan cities like Bangalore and Delhi. The research paper looks into the relationship between the tendency to buy cosmetics in the heat of the moment and their utility.

4. Results and Discussion

The research's results section aims to shed light on the complex relationship between dark pattern marketing and Indian teens' purchase decisions. This section provides an extensive analysis of the prevalence of dark patterns, teen awareness, and the apparent influence on their purchasing behavior based on a careful review of both quantitative and qualitative data.

Overall results

One of the questions asked was of exposure to dark pattern marketing and of the 46 participants, a meager 8.7% (Figure 4.) were actually aware of what the term actually meant. This however did not mean that the other 91.3% did not experience it, in fact it was the opposite as not only everyone experienced these tactics, they actively ignored them as 78.2% of the participant pool ignored the cookie messages and did not read through the terms and conditions which demonstrates the lack of awareness of internet security as well as dark pattern marketing which thrives off of particularly this trait of human behavior.

When asked if the participants felt an increased pressure to consume because of the limited offers and countdowns, a surprising 65.2% of the people answered that they did not. This meant that the patterns had no conscious effect over the individuals who could then make their purchases rationally by thinking them through. However, the others who reported increased stress about the product said that it made them anxious, as if they were losing out on something if they did not buy the product and that oftentimes, they did not even enjoy the product to the extents they would have wished to. Another observation talked about being deceived by firms using these tactics as they witnessed the same offer with the countdown being reintroduced before the previous one ran out so that the firms could profit off of the pressure created to consume. Often making these decisions under such pressures do not come with positive views as 72.7% (Figure 5.) reported that they felt that the purchase was unnecessary after being made and 73.6% of them felt annoyed, cheated and regretful that they made the purchase in the first place.

Correlational Tests

This then raises the question of whether dark pattern marketing has a quantifiable effect on the purchases made. The answer found to that through secondary research is that unknown

dark patterns lead to an increase in sales as more people are prompted to purchase and that also on a sudden and immediate level. This means that because of hidden tactics, emotional vulnerability of the consumers is targeted and twisted to boost purchases and increase revenue for the firms. There are several firms in the beauty industry like Lakmé Cosmetics which use non-exhaustive sales and countdowns which never end to prompt users into purchasing as a consequence of the loss aversion fallacy which is the psychological phenomenon which states that the pain of losing is psychologically twice as powerful as the pleasure of gaining which basically means that for individuals, not purchasing during a 'sale' feels as if they are losing out or losing money and the pain that comes as a consequence of that is much greater than the pleasure they would have derived out of the product in the first place and that necessarily leads to unwanted purchases and regretted decisions when shopping for products online.

On the data collected, there were several correlation tests run to test the baseline hypothesis and analyze the behaviors to a greater extent. There were 4 correlations which had a high expectations of strong positive correlation. The correlation as well as the p-values for all correlations were found using excel. The first correlation was found between screen time of observations and their cosmetic purchasing frequency. The results showed that despite people having high screen times, it did not automatically lead to higher purchasing frequency as the correlation was weak positive at 0.2 and a p-value of 0.17 (Figure 7) The reason for this could be the fact that because this data set included multiple genders and largely high school students, there would have been discrepancies because as general trends suggest, men do not prefer buying cosmetics, it may also show that the wave of cosmetics has yet to reach Indian teenage households especially considering the fact that it is not allowed in most schools. This also shows how research done on the same phenomena in different culture or settings have a direct impact on the results and conclusions drawn by the researchers. This also does not influence the understanding of dark pattern marketing or its validity, rather faces a minor setback as a consequences of the restricted sample size.

The frequency of purchasing was then linked to how they felt about their purchasing decisions, (necessary/unnecessary) and it was found that for this as well, the correlation was weak at 0.3 and a p-value of 0.09 (figure 8). Suggesting that there is no direct strong correlation between how often observations consume and how they feel about the data. This could mean that while they feel that their purchases could have been largely unnecessary as

73% of observations said yes when asked the question individually, the reason why the correlation could have been weak is because the frequency of purchasing is less and while there are some avid buyers, most land at rarely consuming which means that the correlation is weak, it however still leaves possibility of a correlation. The correlation was expected to be higher and closer to 1 based on secondary data as it is largely noticed that people are usually unsatisfied with some aspect of their impulsive purchasing decisions.

Following this, there was a correlation found between the emotions attached to the purchasing and how it impacts their future purchasing decisions. This basically was to see if people had largely negative views about a purchase, if they feel that it was redundant and unsatisfactory, would it lead them to make better purchasing decisions in the future. There was a 0.18 correlation and a 0.3 p-value (figure 9). While the views for purchasing decisions was largely negative, the observations did not catch themselves repeating it and continued in the cycle of unnecessary purchasing influenced by dark pattern marketing. (Figure 2.) This was the only correlation falling in line with the hypothesis that influence of the tactics are long lasting and so subtle that it is hard to actually figure out its effects and work on them. This is in line with what Kim et al 2013 concluded about how the dark marketing tactics interact with a persons moral identity to influence fairness and behavior.

Lastly, a correlation was drawn between a direct dark pattern marketing like the product having a pop-up about it being 'almost sold out' and its impact on their purchasing decision and whether it increased their need to buy that product. The correlation between the two was 0.2 and a p-value of 0.18 (figure 10) which was largely unexpected as according to all secondary research, the need to buy increases as a consequence of such marketing tactics. This could have happened because the demographics is restricted to the younger generation who have active online presences who are already aware of the way marketing works and are therefore less affected by these phenomenon as compared to the older generation.

5. Discussion

A major factor which played the most important role in the study when analyzing the responses was culture. The hypothesis were developed from a western viewpoint as there is not a lot of literature present about the topic which studies the trend in India or in the beauty industry. Since the topic is niche and the sample size relatively small, culture has a large influence. As most of the respondents were from the same age group and place, it can be

concluded that the same make up trends that have picked up in the western world have not come in India yet as men using cosmetics is still considered weird and looked down upon as well as girls using too much makeup. Cosmetics are usually also largely not allowed in schools and for the age demographic who responded, buying cosmetics seem a rare luxury as they have little to no use for it. Other than that, since the responses are largely from the younger generation, despite not being aware of the technical term, because of having online presences, they are all largely exposed to dark pattern marketing on a day to day basis and are aware of etiquette to follow when having to deal with the heavy site traffic and never ending sales and many of them even identified how they seemed to try to guilt the consumer into spending with offers that they cannot refuse.

Figure1 : F1-F6 represents the data from the survey. F6 is the bar graph for purchasing of cosmetics. F7-F10 represents the correlation matrix of different variables.

	<i>How often do you buy cosmetics?</i>	<i>screen time</i>	<i>P-value</i>
How often do you buy cosmetics?	1		
screen time	0.209364708	1	0.1605959
F7: Correlation matrix between frequency of purchasing and screen time			

	<i>How often do you buy cosmetics?</i>	<i>unnecessary purchase</i>	<i>P-value</i>
How often do you buy cosmetics?	1		5.023E-05
unnecessary purchase category	0.27020895	1	0.0917398
F8: Correlational matrix of frequency of cosmetics and how they feel about it			

	<i>feel after purchase</i>	<i>do again</i>	<i>P-value</i>
feel after purchase	1		
do again	0.163578946	1	0.3404494
F9: Correlational matrix of emotions after a purchase and tendency to repeat such purchases.			

	<i>almost sold out</i>	<i>purchasing decision</i>	<i>P-value</i>
almost sold out	1		
purchasing decision	0.209699443	1	0.182574492
F10: correlation matrix between products being almost sold out and its effect on purchasing decision			

Limitations

There are certain limitations of the research like self-reporting bias. As the data was collected through questionnaires, the participants could have been subjected to the bias when answering questions like how much time they spend online and how often they shop as a consequence of being socially desirable. Additionally, as the data set largely consists of schoolmates who might want to seem good and perfect in the questionnaire leading to answering questions in a way where they felt gave them a better image, tampering with the results. The study is also limited by the dynamic nature of the marketing trends. The reason for this is that the effectiveness and prevalence of certain dark patterns may either increase or reduce with the passage of time and other unaccounted advancements in technology. Furthermore, a significant limitation of correlation analysis is that it does not imply causation. Correlation does not prove a cause-and-effect link; rather, it assesses the magnitude and direction of a linear relationship between two variables. Lastly since the participant pool is restricted to one country, there is cultural variation as culture plays a large role in behavior. Despite efforts to maintain ethical standards, ethical considerations in studying vulnerable populations, such as teenagers, present challenges.

The connections and trends found provided insight into how dark pattern marketing affects basic level purchasing decisions and offered possibilities for additional research. It is imperative to take into account the implications of these findings as well as their wider significance for the fields of marketing and policy while also taking into account the shortcomings when evaluating the results. These results add to the body of current knowledge while also providing a foundation for potential future research avenues, policy implications, or practical applications.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provided a nuanced assessment into the widespread impact of dark pattern marketing on Indian youth purchase decisions. Combining quantitative data, which shows how common manipulative marketing strategies are, with qualitative insights, which explore participant emotional and cognitive reactions, provides a thorough grasp of the intricacies present in this field.

The results show that being exposed to dark patterns doesn't have a significant impact on Indian teenagers' decision-making processes and is just a passive experience as one possible explanation could be that it stems as consequence of cultural dissimilarities however, further research is required before conclusions can be drawn. Furthermore, this research has implications that extend above the level of a single person and impact on areas like corporate responsibility, education, and consumer protection.

The study makes an important contribution to our understanding of the effects of dark pattern marketing, there are some drawbacks. The broader societal repercussions are made apparent by requests for governmental action to stop unethical marketing tactics, the possibility of educational programs to improve media literacy, and the urging businesses to review their marketing strategies. Essentially, this study provides a basis for future research, allowing researchers to investigate deeper the long-term consequences of dark pattern marketing, the efficacy of potential solutions, and the cultural differences that could influence such interactions. Through tackling these complexities, researchers, managers, and businesses may collaborate to cultivate a more coherent, moral, and conscientious marketing environment that protects the welfare of consumers—especially the vulnerable group of Indian teenagers. The study helps increase and raise concern over the unethical practises and brings light to how it proves to be harmful to all parties involved in the long term. There should also be

established mechanisms that the consumers can use to report firms engaging in dark pattern marketing. All of this however would not be feasible unless there is increased awareness of the issue in the common public and the government and the policy makers take active steps to help curb the issue.

References

Analyzing the Indian E-Commerce Logistics Market. (n.d.). Retrieved from GLG website:

<https://glginsights.com/articles/analyzing-the-indian-e-commerce-logistics-market/>

Bösch, C., Erb, B., Kargl, F., Kopp, H., & Pfattheicher, S. (2016). Tales from the Dark Side:

Privacy Dark Strategies and Privacy Dark Patterns. *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2016(4), 237–254.

<https://doi.org/10.1515/popets-2016-0038>

Cara, C. (2019). Dark patterns in the media: A systematic review. *Network Intelligence Studies*, 7(14), 105-113.

Correa, S. (2022, February 16). 4 Reasons to Steer Clear of Dark Patterns in e-commerce.

Retrieved from Tavano Team website:

<https://tavanoteam.com/suite-commerce-advanced/4-reasons-to-steer-clear-of-dark-patterns-in-e-commerce/>

Day, G., & Stemler, A. (2019). Are Dark Patterns Anticompetitive? *SSRN Electronic Journal*.

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3468321>

‘Explainer: what is loss aversion and is it real?’ (2018, August 20). Retrieved April 28, 2024, from University of Queensland website economics.uq.edu.au

<https://economics.uq.edu.au/article/2018/08/explainer-what-loss-aversion-and-it-real>

ForumIAS. (2023, July 1). Dark Patterns: Explained, pointwise. Retrieved from

<https://forumias.com/blog/dark-patterns-explained-pointwise/#gsc.tab=0>

- Gambino, A., Kim, J., Sundar, S. S., Ge, J., & Rosson, M. B. (2016). User Disbelief in Privacy Paradox. *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2851581.2892413>
- How India Shops Online 2021. (2021, August 17). *Bain*. Retrieved from <https://www.bain.com/insights/how-india-shops-online-2021/>
- IJRASET. (n.d.). E-commerce Revolution: Exploring the Impact of Online Shopping on Traditional Retail. Retrieved from www.ijraset.com website: <https://www.ijraset.com/research-paper/e-commerce-revolution-exploring-the-impact-of-online-shopping>
- Kim, K. (Kathy), Kim, W. G., & Lee, M. (2023). Impact of dark patterns on consumers' perceived fairness and attitude: Moderating effects of types of dark patterns, social proof, and moral identity. *Tourism Management*, 98, 104763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2023.104763>
- Luguri, J., & Strahilevitz, L. J. (2020). Shining a Light on Dark Patterns. *Journal of Legal Analysis*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jla/laaa006>
- Maheshwari, R. (2023, June 14). Online Shopping And Its Advantages. Retrieved from [Forbes Advisor INDIA](http://www.forbes.com/advisor/in/credit-card/advantages-of-online-shopping/) website: <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/in/credit-card/advantages-of-online-shopping/>
- Mathur, A., Mayer, J., & Kshirsagar, M. (2021). What Makes a Dark Pattern... Dark? Design Attributes, Normative Considerations, and Measurement Methods. *ArXiv:2101.04843 [Cs]*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445610>
- Pomeranz, J. L. (2011). Federal Trade Commission's authority to regulate marketing to children: deceptive vs. unfair rulemaking. *Health Matrix (Cleveland, Ohio: 1991)*, 21(2), 521–553. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22145524/>

- Ravenscraft, E. (2020, July 29). How to Spot—and Avoid—Dark Patterns on the Web. Retrieved from Wired website: <https://www.wired.com/story/how-to-spot-avoid-dark-patterns/>
- Runge, J., Wentzel, D., Huh, J. Y., & Chaney, A. (2023). “Dark patterns” in online services: a motivating study and agenda for future research. *Marketing Letters*, 34(1), 155–160. Retrieved from https://econpapers.repec.org/article/kapmktlet/v_3a34_3ay_3a2023_3ai_3a1_3ad_3a10.1007_5fs11002-022-09629-4.htm
- Sin, R., Harris, T., Nilsson, S., & Beck, T. (2022). Dark patterns in online shopping: do they work and can nudges help mitigate impulse buying? *Behavioural Public Policy*, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1017/bpp.2022.11>
- Trzaskowski, J. (2023, June 26). Persuasion, Manipulation, Choice Architecture and “Dark Patterns.” Retrieved April 28, 2024, from Ssrn.com website: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4491820
- Voigt, C., Schlögl, S., & Groth, A. (2021). Dark Patterns in Online Shopping: of Sneaky Tricks, Perceived Annoyance and Respective Brand Trust. *HCI in Business, Government and Organizations*, 143–155. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77750-0_10
- Waldman, A. E. (2020). Cognitive biases, dark patterns, and the “privacy paradox.” *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 31(1), 105–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2019.08.025>